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FW typical walking stick veinal fusions and reductions

FW Bacillidae: Obriminae

Malaya

CAL Academy, San Francisco

unsorted mat.

CAL ACADEMY
S. Francisco

♀

length 8 cm
FW = $\frac{3}{4}$ of HW length
brown, mottled

FW Phasmatodea: Indonesia, Ambon, Waai Bishop Museum, Hawaii

HW Phasmatodea: Indonesia, Ambon, Waai Bishop Museum, Hawaii

FW Phasmatodea: Very large Malayi Bishop Museum, Hawaii

HW Phasmatodea incetae sedis interesting veinal fusions

HW Palophidae: *Palophus*

FW Palophidae: *Palophus* 3 Dimensional Articulation

JP

Basivenerale Sc (B-Sc) is hidden under BR. Jugal row reduced
Proxalaria of PC&C, Sc, R, J reduced

FW Palophidae: *Palophus* Papua New Guinea

BSc is hidden under BR!

brownish, mottled

HW Palophidae: *Palophus* sp.

Papua New Guinea
CAL Acad. San Francisco

Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla enceladus*

largest Australian stick insect

FW Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla titan*

FW Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla titan*

FW Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla titan*

AA 1+ reduced! (autapo)

HW Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla titan*

HW Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla titan*

HW Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla titan*

FW Phasmatidae: *Acrophylla titan*

FW Phasmatidae close to *Acrophylla titan*

HW Phasmatidae: *Eurycnema* sp. Australia

strangely derived 3Ax - check!

HW Phasmatidae: *Eurycnema* sp.

FW Phasmatidae: *Eurycnema* sp.

Australia N+E

HW Phasmatidae: *Eurycnema* sp. Australia

Partially reduced third axillary, 1st axillary tip probably hidden under 2Ax.

FW

Phasmatidae: *Eurycnema* sp.

Australia

FW

Phasmatidae

New Guinea

CAL. Acad. San Francisco

FW Base Phasmatidae: *Phasma* sp.

HW base Phasmatidae: *Phasma* sp.

FW Phasmatidae: *Platycraninae*

Solomon Is., Bishop Museum

FW Phasmatidae

FW Phasmatidae:

Papua New Guinea, CAL Academy

FW Phasmatodeae unknown genus

HW Phylidae: *Phyllium celebicum*

Phylhidae
Chitoniscus aff.
New Caledonia
&
Fiji

Phylliidae
Chitoniscus aff.
New Caledonia
&
Fiji

Phylliidae: *Phyllium*?

FW Phylliidae: *Phyllium*?

FW Phylliidae: *Phyllium*?

FW Phylliidae: *Phyllium agathysus* Gray

Phylliidae: *Phyllium bilobatum*

HW Phylliidae: *Phyllium bilobatum*

HW length 41mm

HW Phylliidae: *Phyllium celebicum*

FW Phylliidae: *Phyllium*?

Indonesia, Ambon, Waai,
Bishop Museum

FW Phylliidae sister group?

Malay

CAL Acad. Sci.

Phylliidae unknown genus
Malay

HW Pseudophasmatidae: *Acontimetriotes creoxylus*

Pseudophasmatidae: *Prisopus horstokki*

FW Pseudophasmatidae *Prisopus horstokki* Philadelphia Ac. Sci.

HW Pseudophasmatidae: *Prisopus horstokki*

FW Pseudophasmatidae: *Stratocles costaricensis*

brown, mottled l = 8cm

HW Pseudophasmatidae: *Stratocles costaricensis*

